

**Mitigating Impediments to Digital Learning among Post-Literacy Learners:
Next Level Agenda for Adult Learning Practice in Nigeria**

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Abstract

This paper examines various definitions of digital learning, e-learning and digital learning materials. It also discusses types of digital learning materials, nature of post-literacy programmes in Nigeria, post-literacy learning activities available on digital materials, types of digital learning materials, impediments to Digital Learning among Post-Literacy Learners, and among the concluded recommendations that will help in mitigating the impediments as next level agenda for Adult Learning Practice in Nigeria include; teachers and the institutions should be engage in the process of designing and developing digital learning products, and motivation should be provided to learners so that they can be encouraged to face the challenges brought by innovations in the ICT era.

Key words: Digital Learning, E-Learning, ICT, Information Literacy, Impediment, Post-Literacy, and Learners.

Introduction

For more than three decade Nigerians have witnessed higher level of demand in the sector of information communication technology which facilitate teaching and learning among post-literacy adult learners in the various intuitions of higher learning. Information literacy therefore connotes the ability to define what type of information is needed; locate the needed information efficiently; evaluate information and its sources critically; incorporate selected information into one's knowledge base; understand the economic, legal, and social issues surrounding the use of information; and access and use information ethically and legally (American Library Association, 2000). For learning to take place among post-literacy learners effectively, materials for teaching should be identified and be provided appropriately to facilitate an efficient teacher-learner relationship.

Digital learning is used interchangeably with e-learning by scholars in the field of information technology. Yoon, Kwon, and Shim, (2012) stated that digital learning (E-Learning) was first proposed by Jay Cross in 1999. With the development of technology tools, different explanations and terminologies, such as Internet-based training, web-based training, or on-line learning, network learning, and distance learning emerged. Added to this, Holzberger, Philipp, and Kunter, (2013) regarded digital learning as delivery with digital forms of media (e.g. texts or pictures)

through the Internet; and, the provided learning contents and teaching methods were to enhance learners' learning and aimed at improving teaching effectiveness or promoting personal knowledge and skills. Basically, computers and network technology media were applied to learning situations, including synchronous and asynchronous network learning, to break through the restrictions on time, location, and schedule, and to achieve the learner-centered individualized learning (Kaklamanou, Pearce, and Nelson, 2012).). In this era when knowledge and information flow rapidly, the application of digital learning covers different fields and industries. Based on distinct points of view, the definitions are different. Another definition proposed by American Society for Training & Development "ASTD" (2011) is that e-learning is the process whereby learners apply the use of various materials and applications to learning. Therefore e-learning is instruction delivered electronically in every respect by a web browser, through the Internet or an intranet, or through CD-ROM or DVD multimedia platforms. Digital media contain the Internet, corporate network, computers, satellite broadcasting, audiotapes, videotapes, interactive TV, and compact disks. The application includes network-based learning, computer-based learning, virtual classrooms, and digital cooperation. Anttila, Valimaki, Hatonen, Luukkaala, and Kaila (2012) regarded digital learning as a digital tool to acquire digital teaching materials for online or offline learning activity through wire or wireless networks.

The use of e-learning in Nigerian post-literacy learning environment is becoming necessary not because of the nature of the clientele but due to its easiness and efficiency in the delivery of knowledge based information and its user-friendly nature. However, learning in digital learning environments is characterized by the provision of learning materials that are independent of time and location, and by broad access to learning materials. Digital learning environment also supports educational opportunities for all types of learners and provide digitally-enhanced

instruction. Furthermore, a critical observation of post-literacy learning environment in Nigeria reveals that there are some impediments facing post-literacy in accessing, utilization and management of digital learning devices and processes in Nigeria. This paper therefore is a position paper that discusses the impediments to digital learning among post-literacy learners in the Nigerian context. In so doing the paper will discuss what digital learning and/or e-learning is, nature of post-literacy programmes in Nigeria, post-literacy learning activities available on digital materials, types of digital learning materials, impediments to digital learning among post-literacy learners in Nigeria, and offer solutions on mitigating the impediments to digital learning among post-literacy learners as next level agenda for adult learning in Nigeria.

Nature of Post-Literacy Programmes in Nigeria

Post-literacy is a process of continuing education. Its programme and activities are designed to prevent neo-literates and semi-literates from regressing into complete illiteracy. The programmes aim to consolidate the literacy acquired during primary schooling or after the successful completion of the ATLP basic literacy programme (ATLP Volumes 1 to 12). According to UNESCO (1993) post-literacy processes refers to

“processes and activities especially developed for neo-literates, which are designed to help them become fully functionally literate and to be autonomous learners. The essential aims are to prevent regression to semi-literacy or worse and to develop those higher-level literacy skills which are essential for autonomy in learning. Such skills include context vocabulary building, increased general knowledge and its application, and the development of skills in integrating concepts into cognitive systems (schema). It is especially important to develop higher skills of critical reading and to foster skills in independent problem-solving.” (p. 112)

Post-literacy programmes are designed in Nigeria for adults who want to strengthen their literacy skills. They may be immigrants, slum-dwellers or elderly rural poor and more especially adults whom were not opportune for formal school education during their early years. In all activities

the objective is to sustain interest in learning and prevent regression. Literacy regression is common in any society and it is described as follows: -

Literacy regression refers to the situation where learners, having reached a certain level or grade equivalent within a literacy programme, fail to proceed beyond that grade, lose skills and knowledge and revert to a lower grade of skill and functional knowledge. Individuals who are semi-literate may revert to almost or complete illiteracy. Individuals who are almost at the neo-literate stage may revert to semi-literacy and so on. Among school pupils, it is well documented that children who drop-out of formal education before reaching school grade V are likely to regress to almost complete or total illiteracy. Among adults, the boundary is less well-defined but premature withdrawal from adult literacy programmes inevitably leads to regression. The main problem among such people is motivation, which underlines the importance of including functional knowledge of direct and immediate relevance to the learners. Motivational aspects and the problem of regression have considerable implications for continuing education.

Post-literacy programme provide the point of «take-off» in a continuing education system. Without it, continuing education has little meaning to neo-literates or semi-literates.

Post-Literacy Learning Activities Available on Digital Materials

Drill and Practice

Drill and practice programmes are the most well known digital learning materials available in the post-literacy learning environment in Nigeria. Essentially, these programmes built on existing knowledge and give learners the opportunity to consolidate and repeat knowledge and train and automate skills (cf. Weber, 1999). Drill and practice programmes do not have a good reputation nowadays, they are associated with an out of date learning theory in which dull repetition and lower-order thinking are dominant factors. Moreover, drill and practice programmes are

condemned for not optimally using the technological power of new generations of computers. In spite of the many ill-designed drill and practice programmes, this criticism seems to be too harsh. The educational value of these programmes (like all programmes) depends on the quality of its instructional and technical design. And although rather scarce, there are sound drill and practice programmes which also stretch the capabilities of modern computer technology to its limits. An example of such programme is the Dutch programme 'Plato en de rekenspiegel' [Plato and the arithmetic mirror] that provides learners with ample opportunities to practice their numeric skills. This programme consists of excellent facilities to diagnose performance and give adequate feedback and guidance. The programme calculates a model of the learner, and based on his/her past performance, subsequent tasks are given. Feedback is also provided by means of suggesting and supporting different calculating strategies.

Tutorial

Contrary to drill and practice programmes, tutorials support the acquisition of knowledge and/or skills. Tutorials mostly offer pre-defined sequences to build up the desired knowledge and skills. They often apply immediate feedback to guide learning in an effective way. Tutorials are very common in learning software applications (for example: <http://training.ase.tufts.edu/>) But tutorials may also serve instructional purposes in school subjects. The reputation of tutorials is better than that of drill and practice programmes, although also tutorials fit more easily in a tradition of knowledge transmission than in more constructivist visions on teaching and learning. The 'law of cosines' is an example of a tutorial for the subject area Mathematics. The tutorial is developed by the International Education Software [IES]. In this tutorial the learner gets information about the law of cosines. First, the most important formulas are presented. In the second part of this tutorial the theorem is proved by means of five arguments supported by

means of a figure. At the bottom of this web-based tutorial (scrolling down the site), the learner can carry out some tasks about the ‘law of cosines’ in a Java Applet. (<http://www.ies.co.jp/math/products/trig/applets/yogen1/yogen1.html>).

Multimedia

Multimedia (or hypermedia) refers to programmes that contain text, images and sound which are interacted in a non-linear structure. The structure of the information may best be typified as randomly sequenced. Like tutorials, multimedia is primarily designed for the acquisition of knowledge. The essential difference between the two lies in the organization of information: linear or branched sequences in tutorials and randomly sequences in multimedia programmes. This latter sequence allows user to pursuit according to a self-chosen path. Moreover, multimedia programmes usually have a large amount of the information codified in a non-text way, such as pictures, animations and video. Presenting information in a multimedia programme is especially appropriate in ill-structured and complex knowledge domains in which opinions differ. Teacher knowledge is an example of such a domain. Therefore multimedia are apt for teacher education. In Figure 3 an illustration of such a programme, in the form of a multimedia case, is pictured. The MUST (Multimedia in Science and Technology) multimedia-case ‘Kleur & Licht’ [Colour & Light] is a multimedia-programme for pre-service teachers. The MUST-project is a joint venture on behalf of three Teacher Education Colleges, the National Institute for Curriculum Development and the University of Twente in the Netherlands. The project aims at developing multimedia-cases and support tools for Dutch teacher education. In the ‘Colour & Light’ production the overall theme is the learning process that starts from pupils pre-concept. (<http://projects.edte.utwente.nl/crc/must/>)

Simulations

Simulations are programmes that contain a model of a system or a process (De Jong & Van Joolingen, 1998). The manipulation of variables is essential for learning with simulations. Alessi and Trollip (2001) give a simple but clear distinction between two types of simulations. Either, simulations are about something or about how to do something (p.214). The former (physical simulations) focuses on an object or a phenomenon, the latter (procedural simulations), concentrates on a sequence of actions to reach a goal. Physical simulations may have a time component, which implies that users run a simulation, for example, about photosynthesis, as the system unfolds. Time is not a factor in for example a simulation about ‘The influence of the number of foxes on the population of rabbits’, because the learner may iteratively manipulate the variables, by going back to a default option and start the process with other values.

Simulations are sometimes perceived as archetypes for the power computer technology may bring to education and are therefore often associated with constructivist orientations. However, simulations may also design with a behaviouristic orientation in mind. Despite of the orientation, the educational potential of computer simulations is high, because simulations optimally use the interactive possibilities of computer technology. Moreover, simulations allow to handle situations that would be too dangerous or time-consuming in real life. The flight simulator, such as ‘Microsoft Flight simulator 2000’ is a well-known example of a simulation that enables pilots to train crash scenarios. (<http://library.thinkquest.org/27948/collision.html>)

Educational Games

Educational games are sometimes perceived as simulations. However, games neither necessarily are based on a model of reality, nor is playing a game mainly aimed at learning such a model. Nevertheless, sometimes the distinction is difficult. For example, high quality business games

are best classified as simulations, because a model of reality ground their operation. But there are also computer games, for example combat games that are only designed for entertainment and do not have any educational value. Games are difficult to define and may be best described by some characteristics such as: rules, points, winning and losing, coping with pressure, skill & luck and so on. Educational games have a (often hidden) learning purpose. The knowledge and skills are imparted entertainingly into the game. The new words educatainment or funderstanding refer to this integration of play and learning. That brings us to the most distinctive educational feature of games, their quality to arose high motivation amongst learners. ‘Splat!’ is an online educational game about number estimation. In this game the player helps the mop ‘Greg Gunk’ to make the yellow smiley ‘Sunny Jim’ disappears. In this game ‘Sunny Jim’ rotates around ‘Greg Gunk’. The player has to estimate the angle between the stalk of the mop and the position of ‘Sunny Jim’. After entering this angle in the fill-box on the screen, ‘Greg Gunk’ makes the rotation and fires some green soap. If the estimated angle is correct then the green soap hits ‘Sunny Jim’. After hitting ‘Sunny Jim’ for five times, the remainder time will be converted to points en the player enters the next level of the game. So, the better the player estimates the angle between the stalk of the mop and the position of ‘Sunny Jim’, his or her score will be. (<http://www.numeracyresources.co.uk/sunny.html>)

Types of Digital Learning Materials

The prospects of digital learning materials for educational innovations are oblique high. A sober look at the impact of digital learning materials shows that these high expectations are not met. But, there is still a growing conviction that digital learning materials gain significance for learning in school and non-school settings in Nigerian post-literacy learning environment. In order to give a valid examination of the value of digital materials for learning purposes within

the Nigerian context, it is necessary to be more precise about the specific characteristics and educational potential of these materials.

A classical book concerning computers in education is “The computer in the school: Tutor, Tool or Tutee (Taylor, 1980). In this book, computer use for educational purposes is divided in three classes. First, the computer may function as a tutor, which organizes content and delivers instruction. Second, the computer may be seen as a tool, which is used to support student learning activities. And third, the computer may be perceived as tutee, referring to the computer as programmable machine that can take actions according to the instructions of the students or teacher. The delivery and communication facilities specific for the Internet were by no means so far-reaching as today. But also the tutorial role of the computer has become more diverse and more easily accessible through powerful personal computers.

Tools

A broad class of digital learning materials consists of computer tools which are basically developed to facilitate teaching and learning. There are tools for writing, calculating, communicating and so on. These tools are not content-related, and most of them, such as word processing programmes, are not designed with an educational purpose in mind. An encompassing classification of tools is very difficult to formulate (Allessi & Trollip, 2001). In order to provide some structure, we label the computer tools in the following broad categories:

- databases and encyclopedias;
- electronic performance support systems [EPSS];
- communication and cooperative environment;
- new tutees.

Databases and encyclopedias

Databases and encyclopedias are topic-related collections of information. The emphasis of these tools is on quick information search and retrieval and not on (in-depth) learning. Although not always designed for educational purposes, the use of databases and encyclopedias, also in non-digital form, have impacted education since a long time. Thinking about geography without an atlas, or preparing a paper without an encyclopedia would be difficult.

Electronic Performance Support Systems [EPSS]

According to Gery (1991) an EPSS provides integrated information, advice and learning opportunities to improve user performance. Stevens and Stevens (1995, p.238) define an EPSS as a ‘computer-based tool designed to support access to job or task information by providing any or all of the following: training, reference information and expert advice, on demand as needed by the worker.’ In spite of the fact that there are many names and descriptions given to an EPSS, the most important function of an EPSS is to improve the job or task performance by means of a computer.

Communication and collaborative environments

This is the most salient factor of the internet is its functionality as communication medium. E-mail, bulletin boards, chat-rooms and audio- and video-conferencing are devices that facilitate all kinds of communication forms and patterns amongst people engaged in learning globally. Most of these devices do not have a strong association with education. But, communication and collaboration programmes can potentially be powerful educational tools, when they meet the following requirements (Weber, 1999):

- There is an educationally relevant issue;

- This issue is placed within an educational context in which teaching and learning principles are applied;
- An institution (school, company, university etc.) provides the infrastructure and takes the educational responsibility.

An essential feature of communication and collaborative environments is that they permit learning beyond school and country borders. Especially in distance education but also in campus-programmes of universities, there is a growing use of electronic or digital learning environments.

The new tutees

The new tutees are programmes in which the content or the way of action has to be delivered by the users. There are different types of these tools, namely: tools that are used to create, edit, arrange and complement text, music and fixed or moving pictures (Microsoft Word, Adobe Photo Shop) and tools that are used to develop new programmes, like computer programming and authoring languages (HTML-editors, Microsoft Visual Basic, Macromedia Author ware, C++).

Some of digital materials utilized by post-literacy learners in Nigeria include the following hardware and applications:

- i. Discussion-boards;
- ii. Electronic-boards;
- iii. CD-ROM;
- iv. DVD multi-media platforms;
- v. Computers;
- vi. Audio-tapes;
- vii. Video-tapes;

- viii. Interactive TV;
- ix. Digital compact disc;
- x. Projectors;
- xi. Handsets;
- xii. I-phones;
- xiii. Palmtops;
- xiv. Tablets; etc

Impediments to Digital Learning among Post-Literacy Learners in Nigeria

There are obviously barriers identified to digital learning among post-literacy learners in Nigeria. These barriers were those identified within the institutions undertaking post-literacy programmes. Some of these barriers were justified in various empirical studies at both the international and national levels. The identified barriers were divided into three different areas; personal factors, institutional and cultural factors, and technical factors. Personal factors include all barriers that are dependent on the person. Institutional and cultural factors contain barriers that are shaped by the institution and which lecturers cannot control. Technical barriers refer to the use of technologies and infrastructure.

Personal factors

Specifically, the additional time needed for the preparation of digital learning is a major impediment for lecturers in the institutions offering post-literacy learning programmes; since there is generally more time needed than in face-to-face teaching. While the post-literacy learners experienced inadequate time for learning through online; for the lecturers with less e-learning experience, the lack of time is often a problem. Another important personal factor regarded as barrier to digital learning among learners in the post-literacy programmes in Nigeria

is inadequate financial support for the learners to acquire necessary materials meant for digital learning. Most of these learners and their teachers could not afford extra digital facilities in their homes including a WI-FI due to its cost in Nigeria. Added to this is poor supply of electricity and high cost of rechargeable battery and solar installations.

Institutional and cultural factors

In Nigerian post-literacy environment, there are two barriers concerning institutional and cultural factors and these are support and recognition; lack of organizational support for planning, organizing and completing online courses. At most of the post-literacy education institutions a variety of approaches are available for lecturers to support the use of digital learning. Training courses are essential parts of the support. A wide range of topics should be offered in training courses, from using specific tools to pedagogical issues, in order to enable lecturers make advanced use of digital e-learning. The number of training courses attended seems to be a key factor in the degree of utilization of learning management systems. Most of the times, unfilled courses are much more likely to be found by lecturers that have not attended any training course. Lecturers that have taken part in three or even more training courses use the learning management system at a much higher level, technically as well as pedagogically. The lack of recognition of online teaching is an impediment to using digital learning. Inadequate funding of faculties to pursue digital learning materials is therefore a major barrier. In addition to this, the lack of recognition was even the biggest barrier to using digital learning. Most of the learners wanting to engage in the post-literacy learning environment were not aware of the digital learning programme.

Technical factors

The technical factors include skills in using digital learning tools, usability, and infrastructure. There is wide agreement in the various studies that lecturers' existing competences influence the

use of digital learning. The range of computer literacy required for the use of digital learning tools in teaching is very wide. The basic level would be tasks such as uploading or storing files. However, the ways to use learning management systems are endless and an exhaustive use of all available options would not be expected. Competent use however, requires knowledge of the learning management system, computer literacy basic legal knowledge and pedagogical skills. Therefore, it comes as no surprise that many teachers believe their teaching would be more effective if they had more skills in using the learning management system. Inexperienced users are more likely to be afraid of the technology itself, of failure, or being embarrassed in front of the students. A common technical impediment is the lack of user-friendliness of learning management systems. Contemporarily, many users are accustomed to the comfortable operation of social networks, such as writing comments or liking something. The handling of learning management systems are therefore often perceived as cumbersome. The existing technical infrastructure has a significant impact on the use of digital learning. This includes not only the reliability of the tools used and the IT support offered but also a stable Internet connection such as WI-FI.

The equipment at the post-literacy institutions in Nigeria were always seen as barrier that hinders or prevents the use of digital learning. Such equipment included computers, tablets, laptops; lack of infrastructure (e.g. no stable Wi-Fi connection). This is important because technical factors also play important role in the sustainability of digital learning projects. In addition, the technologies must be reliable in order to facilitate sustainable use. A reliable infrastructure and skills in using the tools are necessary factors, while user-friendliness is a sufficient factor for the use of digital learning.

In conclusion, however, teachers' existing experience could be the key to mitigating the impediments. Therefore to mitigate these impediments which were one of the agenda for adult learning practice in the Nigerian post-literacy environment, teachers and the institutions should be engage in the process of designing and developing digital learning products. This can be done through organized Seminars, Workshops, Online learning portals, Chat sessions/Discussion groups, Exchange of ideas, etc.

Since the learner is an important factor in education, adult post-literacy learners in Nigeria are far from their instructors so beside their usual difficulties like mental and physical readiness, they have different kind of difficulties and barriers that may extinguish their enthusiasm for learning. Therefore, motivation should be provided to learners so that they can be encouraged to face the challenges brought by innovations in the ICT era. Before starting the course by the adult post-literacy learners we have to check the learners' facilities at their home. It is one of the most important factors for learners to help them in their communication. This can be done through the provision of access to the internet and broadband as the most widespread mode of accessing the internet.

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